

“GIS DECALOGUE” *Plus Edition*

2022 Edition

Edited by: [Francesco Fiermonte](#), [S3+Lab](#), [Politecnico di Torino](#), Italy

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1.a Never use Windows Desktop (or other System Folders such as “Documents”, “Downloads”, “Images” and so on) to store your files and/or projects.

1.b Meditate and plan at well your working space.

1.c Place the working package (project file, data, tables, and docs) into a convenient structure of folders.

2. Use “relative path” option in your GIS project always.

3. Don’t work on files stored on USB pen drive and / or other USB external devices.

4.a Don’t use long file names.

4.b Don’t use long folder names.

5. Never use special characters, accents, spaces and other <strange> symbols.

6. Add (a short) suffix to file name to describe the process about the data creation.

7. Remind to make backup often.

8. Use a text editor in order to track (and describe) your work.

9. Consider to “switch” from *shapefile* towards a (new) GIS compliant container.

10. (if the internet connection is “OK”) Prefer <base maps> “as services” (WMS, WCS, WFS, Tile Servers, ...).